

DETERMINING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SEISMIC BARRIERS BY CHANGING THEIR THICKNESS

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Abstract. *In the article, the impact of seismic surface waves on the building was determined using the Plaxis 3D software complex using the Finite Element method. The highest displacement amplitudes at each point are determined. Seismic barriers of 0.4 meters, 0.6 meters, 0.8 meters and 1.0 meters of thickness are modeled and their effectiveness by reducing seismic surface waves is studied and a comparative comparison is made.*

Keywords: *building, seismic surface waves, finite element method, theory of elasticity, seismic barrier.*

Introduction

Seismic barriers play a crucial role in reducing damage caused by natural disasters, especially earthquakes. By providing seismic protection to buildings and structures, seismic barriers help safeguard human life. The primary function of seismic barriers is to reduce damage to building structures by absorbing, reflecting, or dissipating seismic energy.

Seismic surface waves can move through a semi-space and cause significant damage to buildings. Seismic barriers, particularly in high seismic activity areas, play an important role. These barriers can be constructed using various materials and technologies, and their effectiveness depends on factors such as height, material quality, and construction methods. For instance, the height of the barrier directly affects its ability to reflect or dissipate seismic waves, making it crucial to evaluate and optimize this factor accurately.

Research Materials and Methodology

The goal is to analyze the effectiveness of seismic barriers by varying their thickness and to determine the optimal thickness. This analysis will help understand how thickness affects seismic waves and identify the most effective and cost-efficient thickness.

In the examined case, the dependence of the seismic barrier's effectiveness on its placement in relation to the impact of Rayleigh surface waves on the building is determined and compared.

To solve the problem numerically, a finite model with dimensions of 200 m in length, 100 m in width, and 50 m in depth was selected. In the problem, groundwater is assumed to be at a depth of 20 m.

The building is 24 m in length, 24 m in width, and 14.75 m in height, with a floor height of 3.3 m, and the basement part of the building is located at a depth of 3 m. The first layer of soil is modeled as 5 meters of loamy sand (Loam), and the second layer is modeled as 45 meters of gravelly soil (Pebble) (Figure 1).

The circular vertical seismic barrier is positioned 28 meters from the center of the building, with a thickness of 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1 meter and a height of 3 meters (Figure 4).

In this problem, an infinite semi-space is replaced by a finite domain. The following conditions are imposed at the boundaries to ensure the waves approach infinity [1,2,3].

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_x &= a\rho V_p \dot{u} \\ \tau_{yz} &= b\rho V_s \dot{v} \\ \tau_{zy} &= b\rho V_s \dot{w} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad \left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_y &= a\rho V_p \dot{v} \\ \tau_{xz} &= b\rho V_s \dot{w} \\ \tau_{zx} &= b\rho V_s \dot{u} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad \left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_z &= a\rho V_p \dot{w} \\ \tau_{xy} &= b\rho V_s \dot{u} \\ \tau_{yx} &= b\rho V_s \dot{v} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

The research domain is divided into 46,782 finite elements and 85,813 nodes. The shapes of the finite elements are chosen as irregular tetrahedra (Figure 2).

The order of the system of differential equations of motion is $85,813 \times 3 = 257,439$. The kinematic relations can be formulated as follows [1,2,3]:

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{u} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1. Discretization of the soil model and residential building into finite elements.

L^T - Transposed differential operator

$$\mathbf{L}^T = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} & \mathbf{0} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

In general, each element material may have an initial deformation due to temperature changes, expansion, or crystallization [1,2,3]. If we denote this deformation by $\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0\}$, the stress is determined by the difference between the current deformation and the initial deformation. Additionally, it is convenient to consider that there might be residual stress that can be measured at the time of observation [1,2,3]. This stress is added to the general expression for stress. When considering the material of the body as elastic, the relationship between stress and deformation is linear [1,2,3]:

$$\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\} = [\mathbf{D}](\{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}\} - \{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_0\}) + \{\boldsymbol{\sigma}_0\} \quad (4)$$

Here, $[\mathbf{D}]$ is the elasticity matrix representing the material properties.

In the case of plane stress, the three components of stress corresponding to deformation are written as follows [1,2,3]:

$$\{\boldsymbol{\sigma}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}$$

The matrix $[\mathbf{D}]$ is determined from the following relationship between stress and deformation:

$$\varepsilon_x - (\varepsilon_x)_0 = \frac{1}{E}\sigma_x - \frac{\nu}{E}\sigma_y; \quad \varepsilon_y - (\varepsilon_y)_0 = -\frac{\nu}{E}\sigma_x + \frac{1}{E}\sigma_y;$$

$$\gamma_{xy} - (\gamma_{xy})_0 = \frac{2 + (1 + \nu)}{E}\tau_{xy};$$

From this:

$$[D] = \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \nu & 0 \\ \nu & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1-\nu}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The system of differential equations for the motion of a mechanical system subjected to dynamic loads is expressed as follows [1,3]:

$$M\ddot{\mathbf{u}} + C\dot{\mathbf{u}} + K\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{F} \quad (6)$$

Here, M is the mass matrix, C is the damping matrix, K is the stiffness matrix, and F is the dynamic load vector. $\mathbf{u}$ is the displacement vector, $\dot{\mathbf{u}}$ is the velocity vector, and $\ddot{\mathbf{u}}$ is the acceleration vector, which are considered continuous functions of time [2,3].

In the numerical formulation of dynamic problems, the time iteration formulation is a crucial factor for the stability and accuracy of the computational process [3].

We adopt the time iteration coefficients for the Newmark method coefficients $\alpha = 0.25$ and $\beta = 0.5$ [2,3]. The properties of the soil, building, and seismic barrier are provided in Table 1 [2,3].

Table 1

Parameter	Unit of measure	Designation	Name of the soil	
			Loam	Pebble
General Properties of the Soil				
Model type	–	–	Liner elastic	Liner elastic
Soil parameter	–	–	Dried	Dried
The specific gravity of the upper layer of the soil under the influence of groundwater	kN/m ³	γ_{unsat}	16	19
The specific gravity of the bottom layer of the soil under the influence of groundwater	kN/m ³	γ_{sat}	17	20.5
Initial porosity coefficient	–	e_{init}	0.5	0.5
Young's modulus	kN/m ²	E	50000	90000
Poisson's ratio	–	ν	0.35	0.3
Longitudinal wave speed	m/s	V_p	218.4	250.1
Transverse wavelength	m/s	V_s	104.9	133.7
General Properties of the Building				
Model Type	–	–	Elastic	
Elasticity Modulus	kN/m ²	E	27500000	
Poisson's Ratio	–	ν	0.2	
Density	kN/m ³	γ	24	
General Properties of the Barrier				
Model Type	–	–	Elastic	
Elasticity Modulus	kN/m ²	E	1000	
Poisson's Ratio	–	ν	0.3	
Density	kN/m ³	γ	12	

To determine and compare the impact of seismic surface waves on the building, 9 observation points per floor, totaling 54 points, were designated for the building (Figure 5) [3].

Figure 2. Observation Points

The propagation of seismic surface waves was generated using a harmonic force. The phase of the harmonic force is 0, with an amplitude of 1 and a frequency of 10 Hz, and a duration of 5 seconds (Figure 6) [3].

Figure 3. Harmonic Force Law

Figure 4. Process of Seismic Surface Waves Affecting the Building

When seismic surface waves impact the building, the maximum amplitude values of u_z at the pre-designated observation points in the building were determined and tabulated (Table 2).

To reduce the impact of seismic surface waves on the building and determine the advantages of different seismic barrier thicknesses, seismic barriers with thicknesses of 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0 meters were modeled. The maximum amplitudes of displacement along the building's u_z axis at designated points (Table 2) were compared and analyzed.

Table 2

№	Observation Points	Coordinates (x, y, z)	No barrier	Barrier			
				0,4 meter	0,6 meter	0,8 meter	1 meter
			Displacement (mm)	Displacement (mm)	Displacement (mm)	Displacement (mm)	Displacement (mm)
The ground part of the building	1	100, 38, -3	1,527	1,521	1,342	1,481	1,305
	2	100, 50, -3	1,518	1,509	1,396	1,497	1,291
	3	100, 62, -3	1,455	1,501	1,403	1,513	1,242
	4	112, 38, -3	0,912	0,609	0,718	0,501	0,503
	5	112, 50, -3	0,825	0,660	0,584	0,556	0,467
	6	112, 62, -3	0,811	0,738	0,485	0,600	0,516
	7	124, 38, -3	0,722	0,772	0,782	0,747	0,630
	8	124, 50, -3	0,772	0,776	0,806	0,737	0,678
	9	124, 62, -3	0,859	0,739	0,798	0,659	0,779
1st floor	10	100, 38, 0,75	1,539	1,531	1,358	1,491	1,312
	11	100, 50, 0,75	1,535	1,528	1,411	1,513	1,301
	12	100, 62, 0,75	1,465	1,515	1,414	1,526	1,254
	13	112, 38, 0,75	0,915	0,609	0,716	0,498	0,505
	14	112, 50, 0,75	0,819	0,662	0,574	0,550	0,465
	15	112, 62, 0,75	0,809	0,740	0,483	0,597	0,513
	16	124, 38, 0,75	0,729	0,775	0,784	0,749	0,633
	17	124, 50, 0,75	0,775	0,778	0,807	0,736	0,681
	18	124, 62, 0,75	0,867	0,739	0,800	0,662	0,779
2nd floor	19	100, 38, 4,05	1,683	1,595	1,439	1,548	1,345
	20	100, 50, 4,05	1,670	1,597	1,473	1,579	1,344
	21	100, 62, 4,05	1,608	1,640	1,467	1,597	1,320
	22	112, 38, 4,05	0,933	0,625	0,720	0,493	0,554
	23	112, 50, 4,05	0,797	0,660	0,550	0,537	0,458
	24	112, 62, 4,05	0,797	0,752	0,482	0,592	0,508
	25	124, 38, 4,05	0,758	0,797	0,789	0,758	0,633
	26	124, 50, 4,05	0,800	0,787	0,813	0,734	0,692
	27	124, 62, 4,05	0,903	0,744	0,815	0,668	0,782
3rd floor	28	100, 38, 7,35	1,822	1,636	1,490	1,588	1,367
	29	100, 50, 7,35	1,802	1,640	1,510	1,621	1,371
	30	100, 62, 7,35	1,742	1,729	1,499	1,645	1,362

	31	112, 38, 7,35	0,950	0,633	0,725	0,490	0,587
	32	112, 50, 7,35	0,785	0,660	0,537	0,531	0,455
	33	112, 62, 7,35	0,790	0,764	0,482	0,589	0,505
	34	124, 38, 7,35	0,782	0,813	0,796	0,765	0,632
	35	124, 50, 7,35	0,819	0,795	0,820	0,734	0,701
	36	124, 62, 7,35	0,938	0,748	0,827	0,673	0,786
4th floor	37	100, 38, 10,65	1,897	1,659	1,517	1,609	1,380
	38	100, 50, 10,65	1,864	1,661	1,529	1,643	1,385
	39	100, 62, 10,65	1,812	1,781	1,518	1,671	1,384
	40	112, 38, 10,65	0,959	0,637	0,728	0,489	0,604
	41	112, 50, 10,65	0,782	0,662	0,532	0,528	0,454
	42	112, 62, 10,65	0,787	0,770	0,481	0,588	0,503
	43	124, 38, 10,65	0,795	0,824	0,804	0,769	0,633
	44	124, 50, 10,65	0,828	0,801	0,825	0,735	0,706
	45	124, 62, 10,65	0,960	0,753	0,835	0,676	0,790
Top Part of the Building	46	100, 38, 13,95	1,919	1,666	1,525	1,616	1,384
	47	100, 50, 13,95	1,878	1,669	1,533	1,649	1,389
	48	100, 62, 13,95	1,832	1,797	1,523	1,680	1,391
	49	112, 38, 13,95	0,960	0,638	0,727	0,488	0,607
	50	112, 50, 13,95	0,781	0,662	0,530	0,527	0,454
	51	112, 62, 13,95	0,786	0,772	0,480	0,587	0,502
	52	124, 38, 13,95	0,800	0,827	0,808	0,770	0,633
	53	124, 50, 13,95	0,832	0,804	0,828	0,736	0,709
	54	124, 62, 13,95	0,966	0,754	0,837	0,677	0,792

Figure 5. Comparison Graph of Displacement at Observation Point 14

In Figure 5, for the building model without any barriers, the maximum displacement along the u_z axis at observation point 14 due to seismic surface waves was $u_{zmax}= 0,819$ mm. For the model with a 0.4-meter thick seismic barrier, $u_{zmax}=0,662$ mm; with a 0.6-meter thick barrier,

$u_{zmax}=0,574$ mm; with a 0.8-meter thick barrier, $u_{zmax}=0,550$ mm; and with a 1.0-meter thick barrier, $u_{zmax}=0,465$ mm. Comparatively, the effectiveness of the seismic barriers was observed as follows: the displacement at observation point 14 with a 0.4-meter thick barrier was reduced by 19.17%, with a 0.6-meter thick barrier – by 29.91%, with a 0.8-meter thick barrier – by 32.84%, and with a 1.0-meter thick barrier – by 43.22%, compared to the model without barriers.

Figure 6. Comparison Graph of Velocity at Observation Point 14

In Figure 6, for the building model without any barriers, the maximum velocity along the v_z axis at observation point 14 due to seismic surface waves was $v_{zmax}=5,64$ cm/s. For the model with a 0.4-meter thick seismic barrier, $v_{zmax}=4,32$ cm/s; with a 0.6-meter thick barrier, $v_{zmax}=3,94$ cm/s; with a 0.8-meter thick barrier, $v_{zmax}=2,20$ cm/s; and with a 1.0-meter thick barrier, $v_{zmax}=1,59$ cm/s. Comparatively, the effectiveness of the seismic barriers was observed as follows: the velocity at observation point 14 with a 0.4-meter thick barrier was reduced by 23.40%, with a 0.6-meter thick barrier – by 30.14%, with a 0.8-meter thick barrier – by 60.99%, and with a 1.0-meter thick barrier – by 71.81%, compared to the model without barriers.

Figure 7. Comparison Graph of Acceleration at Observation Point 14

In Figure 7, for the building model without any barriers, the maximum acceleration along the a_z axis at observation point 14 due to seismic surface waves was $a_{zmax}=92,29$ cm/s². For the model with a 0.4-meter-thick seismic barrier, $a_{zmax}=67,59$ cm/s²; with a 0.6-meter-thick barrier, $a_{zmax}=60,32$ cm/s²; with a 0.8-meter-thick barrier, $a_{zmax}=32,55$ cm/s²; and with a 1.0-meter-thick

barrier, $a_{zmax}=28,70$ cm/s². Comparatively, the effectiveness of the seismic barriers was observed as follows: the acceleration at observation points 14 with a 0.4-meter-thick barrier was reduced by 16.22%, with a 0.6-meter-thick barrier – by 29.73%, with a 0.8-meter-thick barrier – by 55.95%, and with a 1.0-meter-thick barrier – by 69.11%, compared to the model without barriers.

Conclusion

This study investigated the impact of various thicknesses of seismic barriers placed around a building, with a radius of 28 meters and a height of 3 meters, on the seismic surface wave oscillation levels. The results led to the following conclusions:

Impact of Thickness:

For a seismic barrier with a thickness of 0.4 meters, the average reduction in seismic surface wave displacement is 8.40%, velocity is 18.00%, and acceleration is 22.75%.

For a seismic barrier with a thickness of 0.6 meters, the average reduction in displacement is 14.95%, velocity is 36.77%, and acceleration is 33.42%.

For a seismic barrier with a thickness of 0.8 meters, the average reduction in displacement is 15.38%, velocity is 51.98%, and acceleration is 37.77%.

For a seismic barrier with a thickness of 1.0 meters, the average reduction in displacement is 24.05%, velocity is 56.53%, and acceleration is 50.13%.

Effectiveness of Thicker Barriers:

Thicker seismic barriers are more effective at reducing the propagation of surface waves and significantly enhance the seismic safety of buildings.

A 1.0-meter-thick seismic barrier provides the highest level of reduction in surface wave oscillations, thus aiding in improving the safety of buildings in high seismic activity areas.

Practical Significance:

Thicker seismic barriers play a crucial role in protecting buildings from seismic damage, especially in areas with high seismic activity. The findings provide essential information for construction practices aimed at ensuring seismic safety. In summary, increasing the thickness of seismic barriers leads to a significant reduction in seismic surface wave oscillation levels around buildings. This demonstrates their importance in enhancing seismic safety and indicates that using thicker seismic barriers is an effective method for protecting buildings from seismic damage.

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